

A New Framework of Multilevel Analysis with Random Effects Selection for Bayes Optimal Prediction

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Abstract

Multilevel analysis is an essential technique for handling data with a hierarchical structure, commonly known as multilevel data, often encountered in fields like education, biology, and epidemiology. Conventional approaches, such as Hierarchical Linear Models, are widely used for model selection and parameter estimation but often lack statistical optimality for predicting target variables. This study introduces a new framework for multilevel analysis centered on prediction, using Bayesian decision theory to achieve optimal predictions. Our approach incorporates random effect selection, where posterior distributions are weighted to provide Bayes optimal prediction across models, thereby contributing to improved prediction accuracy.

Key Words: Multilevel Analysis, Multilevel Data, Hierarchical Linear Models, Model Selection, Bayesian Decision Theory, Variational Bayes Algorithm

1. Introduction

Multilevel analysis is a statistical technique used to appropriately estimate the sources of variation at each level within hierarchically structured data. Such data with hierarchical structures are generally referred to as multilevel data. Multilevel analysis is valuable when data are sampled from multiple levels, as it allows for the simultaneous evaluation of influences at individual and class levels. A typical example in education is the hierarchical data structure where students belong to classes, and classes belong to schools, requiring separate evaluation of factors at these different levels (Raudenbush & Bryk 2002). Similarly, in epidemiology, a hierarchical structure is standard, with individuals belonging to communities and communities belonging to larger administrative districts. Multilevel analysis is utilized to appropriately assess the impact of community-level social factors on individual health outcomes (Diez-Roux 2000).

In multilevel analysis, hierarchical linear models and linear mixed models are primarily used as statistical models, and analyses considering both fixed and random effects are common (Nan M. Laird & James H. Ware 1982, Nicholas T. Longford 1994, Raudenbush & Bryk 2002, Harvey Goldstein 2010). Fixed effects represent the influence on the entire population. In contrast, random effects represent variations within individual classes or subjects. Previous research has assumed that the design matrices for both fixed and random effects are known, and parameter estimation has been conducted under this assumption (Patterson & Thompson 1971, David A. Harville 1977, Nan M. Laird & James H. Ware 1982, Goldstein 1986).

However, in practical data analysis, which explanatory variables have random effects is often unknown, and this poses a significant challenge in research. Given this context, the problem of random effect selection has become crucial (Stram & Lee 1994, Lin 1997). Model selection approaches using information criteria have been proposed (Hodges & Sargent 2001, Vaida & Blanchard 2005, Gurka 2006, Liang et al. 2008, Greven & Kneib 2010). Approaches utilizing regularization terms for random effect selection also exist (Ahn et al. 2012, Fan & Li 2012, Peng & Lu 2012). Furthermore, Bayesian approaches

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for random effect selection have been developed (Chen & Dunson 2003, Saville & Herring 2009, Armagan & Dunson 2011).

On the other hand, predicting the target variable from newly obtained explanatory variables is also a crucial problem in multilevel analysis. Two assumptions can be considered regarding this prediction. The first assumption is that the newly obtained explanatory variables belong to existing classes within the multilevel data. The second is that the new explanatory variables belong to new, previously unseen classes (Jiang & Rao 2003, Jiang 2021). Conventionally, prediction of the target variable using parameter estimation has been the dominant approach (Gelman & Hill 2006, Harvey Goldstein 2010), and is widely employed in various fields. This study focuses on predicting the target variable under the second assumption: New explanatory variables are obtained from new classes. In this scenario, because the random effects of the new classes are unknown, prediction of the target variable requires marginalization over the random effects, resulting in prediction based solely on fixed effect parameters.

Based on the above, this study considers multilevel analysis under the problem setting of predicting the target variable using explanatory variables obtained from new classes when the explanatory variables with random effects are unknown. Conventional approaches have combined model selection based on information criteria such as AIC and BIC with parameter estimation for prediction (Burnham & Anderson 2004, Snijders & Bosker 2012). When predicting the target variable from explanatory variables sampled from new classes, using cAIC (Vaida & Blanchard 2005), an information criterion for random effect selection, is inappropriate. This is because the target of estimation in predicting new classes is not the random effect but the fixed effect. Existing methods primarily aim to identify a single model through model selection and parameter estimation and perform predictions based on that model. However, it is essential to note that these methods need more discussion on the optimality regarding the prediction accuracy of the target variable.

Therefore, in this study, we propose a framework for deriving the Bayes optimal prediction, which minimizes the Bayes risk function based on Bayesian decision theory (James O. Berger 1985), for new explanatory variables sampled from the population. Unlike conventional methods, this Bayes optimal prediction is derived by weighting with the posterior distribution of models rather than selecting a single model through model selection. It should be noted that, in this study, we employ a different prior distribution for the parameters than conventional Bayesian approaches to derive the predictive distribution analytically. This study focuses on the case where the class to which the newly obtained explanatory variables belong is not included in the existing set of classes. Moreover, we assume that both class-level and individual-level explanatory variables are available and proceed with the discussion by assuming a hierarchical linear model between the target and explanatory variables.

The structure of this paper is as follows. Section 2 describes the probabilistic model between target and explanatory variables assumed in conventional multilevel analysis and provides a brief overview of how prediction of target variables and selection of random effects for new classes have been conventionally handled. Section 3 introduces the probabilistic model between target and explanatory variables assumed in this study, along with the prior distributions for parameters, and derives the Bayes optimal prediction based on Bayesian decision theory. Section 4 derives a Bayes sub-optimal prediction, approximating the Bayes optimal prediction using variational Bayes by incorporating posterior distribution weighting. Section 5 presents the results of numerical experiments on simulated data, evaluating the predictive accuracy of the proposed algorithm and examining the behavior of posterior probabilities. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Previous Research

In this section, we discuss the linear mixed model assumed in conventional multilevel analysis (Raudenbush & Bryk 2002, Harvey Goldstein 2010) and the problem sets concerning the selection of random effects under the linear mixed model. Conventional multilevel analysis presumes a probabilistic model for multilevel data, where the following indices are assumed for the target and explanatory variables. Let $j \in \{1, \dots, J\}$ be the class index and $k_j \in \{1, \dots, n_j\}$ the index of individuals belonging to class j . In multilevel analysis, it is sometimes assumed that explanatory variables are available at both the class and individual levels. Thus, the class-level explanatory variables for class j are denoted by a Q -dimensional vector $\mathbf{w}_j \in \mathbb{R}^Q$, the individual-level explanatory variables for individual k_j in class j are denoted by a P -dimensional vector $\mathbf{x}_{jk_j} \in \mathbb{R}^P$, and the target variable is denoted as $y_{jk_j} \in \mathbb{R}$. Additionally, we define $\mathbf{X}_j := (\mathbf{x}_{j1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{jn_j})^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_j \times P}$ and $\mathbf{y}_j := (y_{j1}, \dots, y_{jn_j})^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_j}$, representing multilevel data as $(\mathbf{X}^J, \mathbf{w}^J, \mathbf{y}^J)$. Here, \mathbf{X}^J , \mathbf{w}^J , and \mathbf{y}^J are defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{X}^J := \{\mathbf{X}_j \mid j = 1, \dots, J\}, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{w}^J := \{\mathbf{w}_j \mid j = 1, \dots, J\}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{y}^J := \{\mathbf{y}_j \mid j = 1, \dots, J\}. \quad (3)$$

When explanatory variables at both the class and individual levels are available, multilevel analysis assumes a regression model between the target and individual-level explanatory variables (Level 1 model) and a regression model between the Level 1 model parameters and class-level explanatory variables (Level 2 model). These Level 1 and 2 models are expressed as follows:

$$\text{(Level1)} \quad \mathbf{y}_j = \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \boldsymbol{\alpha}_j + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j \quad (4)$$

$$\text{(Level2)} \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha}_j = \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{u}_j. \quad (5)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j$ follows a normal distribution with mean $\mathbf{0}$ and covariance matrix $\sigma_\varepsilon^2 \mathbf{I}_{n_j}$, and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{P+1}$ represents the regression coefficients unique to each class j . The vector $\boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1)(Q+1)}$ represents the fixed effects, while $\mathbf{u}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{P+1}$ denotes the random effects for class j , assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean $\mathbf{0}$ and covariance matrix Σ_u . The matrices $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j$ represent the individual- and class-level explanatory variable matrices, respectively, and are given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \mathbf{x}_{j1}^\top \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & \mathbf{x}_{jn_j}^\top \end{pmatrix} = (\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{j1}, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{jn_j})^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_j \times (P+1)}, \quad (6)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_j^\top & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_j^\top & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_j^\top \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1) \times (P+1)(Q+1)}. \quad (7)$$

Combining equations (4) and (5), we obtain the following equation:

$$\mathbf{y}_j = \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\beta} + \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \mathbf{u}_j + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j. \quad (8)$$

Note that $\mathcal{N}(\cdot \mid \cdot, \cdot)$ indicates the probability density function of the normal distribution.

Equation (8) is known as a linear mixed model, commonly assumed as a probabilistic model in conventional multilevel analysis. In many conventional models, parameter estimation of the linear mixed model, such as β , Σ_u , and σ_ε^2 , is typically conducted under the assumption that the elements of the individual-level explanatory variables with random effects are known. However, in practice, the explanatory variables with random effects are often unknown, making this a random effect selection problem.

Furthermore, in multilevel analysis, the prediction problem using explanatory variables obtained from new classes is recognized as an important task (see Section 1). For such problem settings, where random effects related to new classes are unknown, prediction via marginalization is more appropriate. Specifically, when new class-level and individual-level explanatory variables are denoted as \mathbf{w}_{new} and \mathbf{x}_{new} , respectively, and the new target variable as y_{new} , we obtain:

$$y_{\text{new}} \sim \mathcal{N}(y_{\text{new}} \mid \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}^\top \beta, \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}^\top \Sigma_u \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}) \quad (9)$$

Conventionally, multilevel analysis has considered methods that address random effect selection and prediction when explanatory variables from new classes are available. In this problem set, as shown in equation (8), random effects are marginalized, so prediction relies solely on the estimated fixed effects. Consequently, for model selection using information criteria, AIC (Akaike 1973) or BIC (Schwarz 1978) based on marginalized likelihood are more appropriate than cAIC, which conditions on the estimated random effects.

3. Proposed Method

In this section, we define the prior distributions for the parameters and derive the Bayes optimal prediction using Bayesian decision theory. In our study, for the random effects associated with the individual-level explanatory variable $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ in equation (8), we denote the model that specifies which dimensions include random effects as m and the set of models as \mathcal{M} . In this case, the probabilistic model between the target variable and explanatory variables is given by:

$$p(\mathbf{y}_j \mid \beta, \mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}, m, \lambda_\varepsilon) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_j \mid \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \beta + \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^{(m)} \mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}, \lambda_\varepsilon^{-1}) \quad (j = 1, \dots, J). \quad (10)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^{(m)}$ and $\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}$ represent the explanatory variable matrix and random effects for class j in model m , with dimension $P^{(m)}$. λ_ε represents the precision of the regression model (inverse of variance σ_ε^2). Next, we assume the following prior distributions for model m and the parameters of equation (10), including β , $\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}$ ($j = 1, \dots, J$), and λ_ε :

$$p(m) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{M}|}, \quad (11)$$

$$p(\beta) = \mathcal{N}(\beta \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta, (\lambda_\varepsilon \mathbf{K}_\beta)^{-1}), \quad (12)$$

$$p(\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m; \mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)} \mid \mathbf{0}, (\lambda_\varepsilon \mathbf{K}_u^{(m)})^{-1}) \quad (j = 1, \dots, J), \quad (13)$$

$$p(\lambda_\varepsilon) = \text{Gam}(\lambda_\varepsilon \mid a_\varepsilon, b_\varepsilon). \quad (14)$$

Here, $\text{Gam}(\cdot \mid \cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the probability density function of the gamma distribution. Additionally, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1)(Q+1)}$, $\mathbf{K}_\beta^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1)(Q+1) \times (P+1)(Q+1)}$, and $\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{(P^{(m)}+1) \times (P^{(m)}+1)}$ are constants. Note that the prior distributions of β and $\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}$ ($j = 1, \dots, J$) are conditioned on λ_ε .

Under these prior settings, the distribution of the target variable y_{new} for a new class is given by:

$$p(y_{\text{new}} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m) = \mathcal{N}\left(y_{\text{new}} \mid \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon^{-1} \left(1 + \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^{(m)\top} \mathbf{K}_u^{(m)-1} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^{(m)}\right)\right) \quad (15)$$

The known data set \mathbf{D} in this study is defined as:

$$\mathbf{D} := \{(\mathbf{X}^J, \mathbf{w}^J, \mathbf{y}^J), \mathbf{x}_{\text{new}}, \mathbf{w}_{\text{new}}\}. \quad (16)$$

Based on Bayesian decision theory (James O. Berger 1985), we derive a prediction (Bayes optimal prediction) that minimizes the Bayes risk function under a squared-error loss between the true new target variable y_{new} from a new class and the predicted new target variable \hat{y}_{new} . The decision function δ in this study is given by:

$$\delta : \mathbf{D} \mapsto \hat{y}_{\text{new}}. \quad (17)$$

At this time, for the squared-error loss between y_{new} and $\delta(\mathbf{D})$, we denote the expected value of the distribution of y_{new} , represented by equation (15), as the loss function $L(\cdot)$. The expected value of the loss function $L(\cdot)$ under the distribution of known data \mathbf{D} is defined as the risk function $R(\cdot)$, and the Bayes risk function $\text{BR}(\cdot)$ is defined as the expected value of the risk function under the distributions of m , $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, $\mathbf{u}^{J(m)}$, and λ_ε . Each function is represented as follows:

$$L(\delta(\mathbf{D}), \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m) = \int_{\mathcal{Y}} (y_{\text{new}} - \delta(\mathbf{D}))^2 p(y_{\text{new}} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m) dy_{\text{new}}, \quad (18)$$

$$R(\delta, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, m) = \int_{\mathcal{D}} L(\delta(\mathbf{D}), \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m) p(\mathbf{D} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, m, \lambda_\varepsilon) d\mathbf{D}, \quad (19)$$

$$\text{BR}(\delta) = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} p(m) \int_{\Theta^{(m)}} R(\delta, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, m) \quad (20)$$

$$p(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \lambda_\varepsilon) p(\mathbf{u}^{J(m)} | \lambda_\varepsilon, m; \mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}) p(\lambda_\varepsilon) d\boldsymbol{\beta} d\mathbf{u}^{J(m)} d\lambda_\varepsilon. \quad (21)$$

where \mathcal{Y} denotes the set of possible values of y_{new} , \mathcal{D} the set of possible values of known data \mathbf{D} , and $\Theta^{(m)}$ the set of possible values of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, $\mathbf{u}^{J(m)}$, and λ_ε , with $\mathbf{u}^{J(m)} := \{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)} | j = 1, \dots, J\}$.

Corollary 1 *The prediction $\delta^*(\mathbf{D})$ that minimizes the Bayes risk function $\text{BR}(\delta)$ is given by:*

$$\delta^*(\mathbf{D}) = \int_{\mathcal{Y}} y_{\text{new}} p^*(y_{\text{new}} | \mathbf{D}) dy_{\text{new}}. \quad (22)$$

where the predictive distribution $p^*(y_{\text{new}} | \mathbf{D})$ is defined as:

$$p^*(y_{\text{new}} | \mathbf{D}) = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \int_{\Theta^{(m)}} p(y_{\text{new}} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m) p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, m | \mathbf{D}) d\boldsymbol{\beta} d\mathbf{u}^{J(m)} d\lambda_\varepsilon. \quad (23)$$

Thus, $\delta^*(\mathbf{D})$, derived from equations (22) and (23), is the Bayes optimal prediction.

4. Bayes Sub-Optimal Prediction

Although the Bayes optimal prediction can be obtained by equations (22) and (23), it is challenging to analytically calculate the posterior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, m | \mathbf{D})$ in these equations. Therefore, in this section, we derive an approximate posterior distribution for $p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \lambda_\varepsilon, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, m | \mathbf{D})$ using the variational Bayes method. We obtain an approximation of equation (22) (Christopher M. Bishop 2006).

4.1 Approximate Posterior Distribution

In this study, we assume the following factorization for $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , λ_ε , and m :

$$q(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m) = q(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m) \left(\prod_{j=1}^J q(\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m) \right) q(\lambda_\varepsilon \mid m) q(m). \quad (24)$$

Under this assumption, we derive the approximate posterior distribution $q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m)$, which minimizes the KL-divergence from the true posterior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m \mid \mathbf{D})$. From equation (24), the following update equations hold for each approximate posterior distribution of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, $\mathbf{u}^{J(m)}$, and λ_ε (Christopher M. Bishop 2006):

$$\ln q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m) = E_{q^*(\mathbf{u}^{J(m)} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m)} [\ln p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, \lambda_\varepsilon \mid \mathbf{D})], \quad (25)$$

$$\ln q^*(\mathbf{u}^{J(m)} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m) = E_{q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m)} [\ln p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, \lambda_\varepsilon \mid \mathbf{D})], \quad (26)$$

$$\ln q^*(\lambda_\varepsilon \mid m) = E_{q^*(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m)} [\ln p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, \lambda_\varepsilon \mid \mathbf{D})]. \quad (27)$$

Based on equations (25)–(27), we update $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, $\mathbf{u}^{J(m)}$, and λ_ε in turn under a given model m . In this study, we update in the order $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, $\mathbf{u}^{J(m)}$, and λ_ε .

4.1.1 Updating $\boldsymbol{\beta}$

From equation (25), the update equation for $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is given by:

$$q^{(t+1)}(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m) = \mathcal{N}\left(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)}}^{(t+1)}, (\lambda_\varepsilon \mathbf{K}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)}}^{(t+1)})^{-1}\right). \quad (28)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)}}^{(t+1)}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)}}^{(t+1)}$ are given by:

$$\mathbf{K}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} = \sum_{j=1}^J \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_j^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_j + \mathbf{K}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \quad (29)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{K}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)}}^{(t+1)-1} \left(\sum_{j=1}^J \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_j^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^\top \left(\mathbf{y}_j - \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^{(m)} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}}^{(t)} \right) + \mathbf{K}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}} \right). \quad (30)$$

4.1.2 Updating $\mathbf{u}^{J(m)}$

From equation (26), the update equation for $\mathbf{u}^{J(m)}$ is given by:

$$q^{(t+1)}(\mathbf{u}^{J(m)} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m) = \prod_{j=1}^J \mathcal{N}\left(\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)} \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}}^{(t+1)}, (\lambda_\varepsilon \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}}^{(m)(t+1)})^{-1}\right). \quad (31)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}}^{(m)(t+1)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}}^{(t+1)}$ are given by:

$$\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}}^{(m)(t+1)} = \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^{(m)\top} \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^{(m)} + \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}}, \quad (32)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)}}^{(m)(t+1)-1} \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^{(m)\top} (\mathbf{y}_j - \widetilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}^{(m)}}^{(t+1)}) \quad (j = 1, \dots, J). \quad (33)$$

4.1.3 Updating λ_ε

From equation (27), the update equation for λ_ε is given by:

$$q^{(t+1)}(\lambda_\varepsilon | m) = \text{Gam}\left(\lambda_\varepsilon \mid a_\varepsilon^{(m)(t+1)}, b_\varepsilon^{(m)(t+1)}\right). \quad (34)$$

where $a_\varepsilon^{(m)(t+1)}$ and $b_\varepsilon^{(m)(t+1)}$ are given by:

$$a_\varepsilon^{(m)(t+1)} = a_\varepsilon + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{j=1}^J n_j + (J + Q + 1)(P^{(m)} + 1) \right), \quad (35)$$

$$b_\varepsilon^{(m)(t+1)} = b_\varepsilon + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^J \left(\left(\mathbf{y}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\beta^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^{(m)} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} \right)^\top \right. \\ \left. \left(\mathbf{y}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_j \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\beta^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} - \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_j^{(m)} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} \right) + \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j^{(m)}}^{(t+1)\top} \mathbf{K}_u^{(m)} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} \right) \\ + \left(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\beta^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta \right)^\top \mathbf{K}_\beta \left(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\beta^{(m)}}^{(t+1)} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta \right). \quad (36)$$

4.1.4 Calculating the Variational Lower Bound

In the variational Bayes method, we use the variational lower bound to evaluate the stopping criterion for updates (Christopher M. Bishop 2006). The variational lower bound at the t -th iteration is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_m^{(t)}(\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}) &:= \int_{\Theta^{(m)}} q^{(t)}(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J^{(m)}} | \lambda_\varepsilon) \ln \frac{p(\mathbf{D}, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J^{(m)}} | \lambda_\varepsilon)}{q^{(t)}(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J^{(m)}} | \lambda_\varepsilon)} d\boldsymbol{\beta} d\mathbf{u}^{J^{(m)}} d\lambda_\varepsilon \\ &= E[\ln p(\mathbf{D} | \boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J^{(m)}} | \lambda_\varepsilon)] + E[\ln p(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \lambda_\varepsilon)] + \sum_{j=1}^J E[\ln p(\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)} | \lambda_\varepsilon; \mathbf{K}_u^{(m)})] \\ &\quad + E[\ln p(\lambda_\varepsilon)] - E[\ln q^{(t)}(\boldsymbol{\beta} | \lambda_\varepsilon, m)] - \sum_{j=1}^J E[\ln q^{(t)}(\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)} | \lambda_\varepsilon, m)] \\ &\quad - E[\ln q^{(t)}(\lambda_\varepsilon | m)]. \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Note that in equation (37), all expectations are calculated with respect to $q^{(t)}(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J^{(m)}} | \lambda_\varepsilon | m)$.

4.1.5 Updating Model m

Using the variational lower bound obtained in equation (37), we can derive the approximate posterior distribution of the model as:

$$q^{(t+1)}(m) = \frac{p(m) \exp\left(\mathcal{L}_m^{(t)}\right)}{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} p(m) \exp\left(\mathcal{L}_m^{(t)}\right)} \quad (38)$$

4.1.6 Updating the Hyperparameter $\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}$

In the variational Bayes algorithm, the hyperparameter $\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}$ is assumed to be constant. However, by differentiating the variational lower bound $\mathcal{L}_m^{(t)}(\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)})$ with respect to $\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}$,

the update equation for $\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}$ is given by (Nakahara et al. 2023):

$$\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)*} = J \left(\sum_{j=1}^J \frac{a_\varepsilon^{(m)(t)}}{b_\varepsilon^{(m)(t)}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j^{(m)}}^{(t)} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{u_j^{(m)}}^{(t)\top} + \mathbf{K}_{u_j}^{(m)(t)-1} \right)^{-1} \quad (39)$$

By substituting $\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)*}$ into equations (32) and (36), it becomes possible to sequentially update $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, $\mathbf{u}^{J(m)}$, λ_ε , m , and $\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}$.

4.2 Bayes Sub-Optimal Prediction

Let T be the iteration count at which the variational lower bound satisfies the convergence criterion. From equation (24), the approximate posterior distribution at iteration T is given by:

$$q^{(T)}(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m) = q^{(T)}(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m) \left(\prod_{j=1}^J q^{(T)}(\mathbf{u}_j^{(m)} \mid \lambda_\varepsilon, m) \right) q^{(T)}(\lambda_\varepsilon \mid m) q^{(T)}(m). \quad (40)$$

Substituting this into equation (23) for the posterior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \mathbf{u}^{J(m)}, \lambda_\varepsilon, m \mid \mathbf{D})$, the Bayes sub-optimal predictive distribution for the new target variable y_{new} is given by:

$$p^*(y_{\text{new}} \mid \mathbf{D}) \approx \text{St} \left(y_{\text{new}} \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{new}}^{(m)}, \lambda_{\text{new}}^{(m)}, \gamma_{\text{new}}^{(m)} \right). \quad (41)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{new}}^{(m)}$, $\lambda_{\text{new}}^{(m)}$, and $\gamma_{\text{new}}^{(m)}$ are given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{new}}^{(m)} = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\text{new}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\beta^{(m)}}^{(T)}, \quad (42)$$

$$\lambda_{\text{new}}^{(m)} = \left(1 + \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\text{new}} \mathbf{K}_\beta^{(T)-1} \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\text{new}}^\top \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}} + \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^{(m)\top} \mathbf{K}_u^{(m)-1} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^{(m)} \right) \frac{a_\varepsilon^{(m)(T)}}{b_\varepsilon^{(m)(T)}}, \quad (43)$$

$$\gamma_{\text{new}}^{(m)} = 2a_\varepsilon^{(m)(T)}. \quad (44)$$

Using the approximate distribution from equation (41), we obtain the Bayes sub-optimal prediction as follows:

$$\delta^*(\mathbf{D}) \approx \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} q^{(T)}(m) \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\text{new}}^{(m)} = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} q^{(T)}(m) \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{new}}^\top \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\text{new}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\beta^{(m)}}^{(T)}. \quad (45)$$

5. Numerical Experiments

In this section, we compare the Bayes sub-optimal prediction method derived in Section 4 with conventional prediction methods using synthetic data. We aim to verify that the proposed method, which minimizes the Bayes risk function for prediction errors by weighting based on the posterior distribution of models, outperforms conventional methods that select a single model through model selection and parameter estimation. Bayes risk function (mean squared prediction error) is used as the performance metric, comparing our approach to conventional methods. We conduct two types of experiments based on different sampling approaches:

- Experiment 1: Fix the class sample size J and increase the individual sample size n_j for each $j \in \{1, \dots, J\}$.

- Experiment 2: Fix the individual sample size n_j within each class and increase the class sample size J .

The experiments follow these steps, where for simplicity we set $P = 2$ and $Q = 0$:

- (i) Generate \mathbf{x}_{jk} and \mathbf{w}_j ($j = 1, \dots, J_p; k = 1, \dots, N_j$) from the standard normal distribution $N(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$.
- (ii) Generate a model m .
- (iii) Fix $\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta$, \mathbf{K}_β , $\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}$, a_ε , and b_ε .
- (iv) Generate $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, \mathbf{u}^J , and λ_ε .
- (v) Generate the target variable y_{jk} ($j = 1, \dots, J_p; k = 1, \dots, N_j$).
- (vi) Perform class and individual sampling from the population to obtain the multilevel data $(\mathbf{X}^J, \mathbf{w}^J, \mathbf{y}^J)$.
- (vii) Sample individuals with new explanatory variables \mathbf{x}_{new} and \mathbf{w}_{new} , make predictions, and compute Bayes risk.
- (viii) Repeat Step (vii) 500 times.
- (ix) Vary the sample size, repeating Steps (vi)–(viii).
- (x) Repeat Steps (v)–(ix) 40 times.
- (xi) Repeat Steps (iv)–(ix) 5 times.

Here, $a_\varepsilon = 80$, $b_\varepsilon = 20$, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_\beta = \mathbf{0}$, $\mathbf{K}_\beta = 13.44\mathbf{I}$, and $\mathbf{K}_u^{(m)}$ is a diagonal matrix with diagonal entries equal to 0.44.

In these experiments, we compare the predictive performance of the proposed method with predictions based on model selection using AIC (Burnham & Anderson 2004, Snijders & Bosker 2012) and predictions based on model selection using the Bayes factor (Gelfand & Dey 1994).

5.1 Experiment 1

In Experiment 1, the class sample size is set to $J = 5$, and the individual sample size is varied as $n_j = 5, 16, \dots, 60$.

5.1.1 Results

Figure 1 shows the approximate Bayes risk function (mean squared prediction error) calculated under the constant settings and conditions specified in the experiment.

Additionally, Figures 2–9 illustrate the behavior of the approximate posterior probability of each model m in the proposed algorithm, considering eight scenarios for the true data-generating model: no random effect, random effects only in the intercept, random effects only in x_1 , and so forth.

5.2 Experiment 2

In Experiment 2, the class sample size is varied as $J = 5, 12, \dots, 40$, while the individual sample size within each class is set to $n_j = 15$.

Figure 1: Approximate Bayes risk function (mean squared prediction error)

Figure 2: No random effects

Figure 3: Random effect in intercept

Figure 4: Random effect in x_1

Figure 5: Random effect in x_2

Figure 6: Random effects in x_0 and x_1

Figure 7: Random effects in x_0 and x_2

Figure 8: Random effects in x_1 and x_2

Figure 9: Random effects in all explanatory variables

5.2.1 Results

Figure 10 displays the approximate Bayes risk function calculated under the specified constants and conditions for this experiment.

Figure 10: Approximate Bayes risk function (mean squared prediction error)

Similar to Experiment 1, Figures 11–18 illustrate the behavior of the approximate posterior probability for each model m under eight scenarios for the true data-generating model: no random effect, random effect only in the intercept, random effect only in x_1 , and so forth.

Figure 11: No random effects

Figure 12: Random effect in intercept

5.3 Discussion

Here, we discuss insights derived from the results of Experiments 1 and 2. The primary objective of this study was to validate the accuracy of the Bayes sub-optimal prediction derived using variational Bayes as an approximation of the Bayes optimal prediction presented in equation (22). Across both experiments, our proposed method consistently yielded the lowest Bayes risk function when compared to conventional approaches,

Figure 13: Random effect in x_1

Figure 14: Random effect in x_2

Figure 15: Random effects in x_0 and x_1

Figure 16: Random effects in x_0 and x_2

Figure 17: Random effects in x_1 and x_2

Figure 18: Random effects in all explanatory variables

confirming that the Bayes sub-optimal prediction closely approximates the Bayes optimal prediction derived in equation (45).

Another aim of these experiments was to evaluate the behavior of approximate posterior probabilities for different models. The results of Experiments 1 and 2 show that, with increased sample sizes, the posterior probability for the true model becomes dominant. Additionally, by comparing Experiments 1 and 2, it is observed that increasing the class sample size J reduces the Bayes risk function in predictions and enables the posterior probability of the true model to converge to one with fewer samples.

6. Conclusion

In this study, we proposed a framework for deriving predictions that minimize the Bayes risk function (Bayes optimal prediction) for new explanatory variables sampled from a population given multilevel data. Unlike conventional methods that determine a single model through model selection, our approach achieves Bayes optimal prediction by weighting based on the posterior distribution of models. Furthermore, we derived Bayes sub-optimal prediction via variational Bayes approximation to the Bayes optimal prediction. Numerical experiments confirm that, across two sampling methods, our proposed method outperforms conventional parameter estimation-based prediction regarding reduced Bayes risk, indicating that it provides an optimal predictive solution.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported in part by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number JP22K02811, JP23K03863, and P23K04293, and by JST SPRING, Grant Number JPMJSP2128.

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